

Ranked Behavioral Parameter	Loading Score
NOR.CP	0.558692469
Grip.force	0.483594389
Forced Swim	-0.445096918
Time.novel.mus	0.431265584
Time.mus.vs.obj	0.261969882
NOR.SP	-0.035632879

Ranked Behavioral Parameter	Loading Score
NOR.SP	-0.667740631
Time.mus.vs.obj	0.492334625
Time.novel.mus	-0.416416692
Grip.force	0.323391524
Forced.swim	0.135690966
NOR.CP	-0.123822813